

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES THROUGH ORGANIZING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article describes the importance of independent education in the formation of professional competencies of students in the higher education system and opinions about the proper organization of the independent education process.

Key words: independent work, competence, practice, seminar, methodology, educational system.

Independent works of students are didactically organized by the teacher and consist of complex actions of the student directed to self-training. The student's learning process occurs without the direct participation of the teacher.

The cost of independent education increases. The amount of information should be changed regularly. According to the calculations of informatics and sociologists, the amount of information in a specific field of human knowledge doubles every 5-6 years. This implies an increase in not only the quantity indicator, but also the quality indicator. The teacher, getting acquainted with new scientific literature, selects and recommends literature that will stimulate the development of the student's intellect within the framework of the course he teaches.

The main types of independent work of students. The types of organization of students' independent work are as follows:

- ❖ Independent work with literature;
- ❖ Seminar, preparation for inspections;
- ❖ Preparation of course project work and BMIs;
- ❖ Pedagogical practice;
- ❖ Preparing lectures for student scientific conferences.

Independent work with literature. First of all, it is necessary to form the skills of working with literature related to the methodology of professional education. In this case, it is necessary to teach the student to effectively use the educational materials in the young book.¹

A number of situations arise in the method of working with text. These include the following:

- ❖ Separate basic phrases and concepts in the text, understand and master the educational material.
- ❖ Clarification of unclear terms and concepts;
- ❖ A deeper approach to the questions that will be considered in training sessions;

The level of difficulty of the questions comes from the purpose of education. If the questions are focused on existing problems in the vocational education methodology, the problems will

¹ Avanesov, V. S. Form of test tasks: a textbook for teachers of schools, lyceums, teachers of universities and colleges. 2nd ed., revised. and extended / V. S. Avanesov. M., 2005.

be solved as a result of discussion. The following methods can be used for independent work with the educational text in the field of vocational education methodology:

- Diary of the student, which is recommended by the teacher, is a database of independent information. The approach, which is divided into prosecutions and negligent aspects is displayed clearly and short.
- Use of cartography in working with the text text. The cartography is the concept and union of instructions. In this case, the student will study the key gestures and the current positions in the form of a group, which is achieved that it will master the content of the studied theme.
- Vocational Education Methodology Discussion method when studying the materials of the teaching materials. In this case, students are given the opportunity to express their independence. A number of questions are underway to organize the discussion of critical situations:

- What does the author want to say, what do you think?

- What uncertainties are there in the obtained results?

- What is your opinion in defense of the author's position?

"Give me the last word" method. The student is given the opportunity to find the most important passage in the existing source and express his opinion on it.

"Mazayka" method. In this case, students study new materials in special small groups and then return to the first group and explain what they have learned.

The "outlining" method. Based on the explanation given by the teacher, he writes a summary of the literature on the topic.

Preparation for seminars and inspections. Preparation for seminars and inspections involves a detailed study of the topic and its content. The teacher's advice, recommendations and guidance play an important role in the preparation of the student for the examinations.²

Preparation of course project work and graduation qualification work. The purpose of writing the course project work and graduation qualification work is to generalize, systematize and deepen the knowledge and skills of students. These will be aimed at professional problems in solving specific vocational education methodology issues. The topic of research can be proposed by the supervisor or the student. In this, the main attention is based on the knowledge the student has learned and the conclusions derived from them. One of the methodological requirements for the student's scientific work is the use of modern research methods, the ability to work with various literatures (foreign and domestic sources), working with the Internet. The composition of the work should be understandable, coherently stated and based on specific sources, with the correct use of scientific terms.

Pedagogical practice. Vocational education students conduct pedagogical practice in the 4th year. The word "practice" comes from the Greek "praxis" meaning action, mastery of activity, it is a method of applying the theoretical knowledge acquired by the student in practice during the educational process. In the period of pedagogical practice, 3 different qualities of a student are manifested:

- knowledge of the field of science;

² Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

- pedagogical skill in teaching this subject;
- interpersonal relationships.

During this period, students read lectures, conduct seminars, participate in mutual classes, and at the end, a report is drawn up.

If we pay attention to today's modern education system, we can see that the skills of pedagogues and their competence are the guarantee of quality education.

The English concept of "competence" literally means "ability". The content serves to illuminate "the effective use of theoretical knowledge in the activity, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional qualifications, skill and talent." The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological research. Therefore, competence is "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, consistently develops and "ownership of a plan of action in complex processes".

Competence is the ability to use the theoretical knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by a student in a specific subject to solve theoretical and practical problems encountered in everyday life.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

Professional competence is evident in the following cases:

- ✓ in complex processes;
- ✓ performing unclear tasks;
- ✓ using conflicting information;
- ✓ A specialist with professional competence in having an action plan in an unexpected situation:
 - ✓ constantly enriches his knowledge;
 - ✓ learns new information; - deeply understands the requirements of the era;
 - ✓ seeks new knowledge;
 - ✓ processes them and uses them effectively in his practical work;

Social competence represents the feeling of responsibility and participation in events or events in society. Striving for professional status growth is also a part of social competence. Social-psychological competence is important for managing the educational system. The meaning of competence as "a person with experience" and "a person who knows well" is often explained in old literature. Currently, competence means how to behave in situations that occur in the educational process, in unexpected situations, openness to communication, ability to move in consistently developing and complex processes.

According to V. N. Vedensky, "Competence is a kind of personal description, and competence is a complex of specific professional or functional descriptions." Summarizing the above points, the manifestation of social competence includes the following:

- ❖ to be active in social relations as a perfect person.
- ❖ to acquire moral qualities, life knowledge, skills and qualifications.
- ❖ being able to communicate with subjects in professional activities.

- ❖ to be sincere in solving problems.
- ❖ creative approach.
- ❖ being able to purposefully use modern methods and tools in the implementation of the educational process.

CONCLUSION.

Proper organization of independent work in education is also important for improving the professional competence of students. The main essence of the organization of independent work is to direct the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in the course of the organized educational process to the improvement of the competences of applying them during their personal life, as well as in professional and social activities.

The goals of teaching in the competence approach are self-awareness by students, understanding of ways to achieve learning goals in the educational process, increasing students' learning and learning activity, through self-development of students as individuals. It is necessary to envisage priority directions such as adaptation to society and independent life, socialization.

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